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*Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

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Contents

Policy brief

I. Introduction	
Who is the Policy Brief for?	4
What is the FIERCE project?.....	4
II. Anti-gender, anti-feminist: what are we talking about?.....	5
Key definitions.....	5
What are anti-gender and anti-feminist movements?	6
What is the « backlash »?	8
The EU Legal Framework of Gender Equality	10
III. What are the consequences and impact?.....	13
IV. What can you do for the upcoming mandate? - Our recommendations	14
• Support European Feminist Networks that promote human rights.....	14
• Better identifying and combating Anti-gender movements	15
• Confront online democracy threats such as disinformation and hate speech.....	15
• Support the implementation of legislation supporting women and gender rights.....	16
 Factsheet - Gender equality under attack- The normalisation of anti-gender movements in Europe.....	 18
 Factsheet - Feminist movements in Europe: a democratic force against the backlash	 23
 Reference.....	 28

[Policy brief]

I. Introduction

Who is the Policy Brief For?

As the European parliamentary elections took place in summer 2024 and as a brown wave swept through the Chamber, welcoming an unprecedented number of far-right MEPs, the rights of women, gender minorities and the most marginalised populations seem to be under threat more than ever.

Yet every time gender equality takes a step backwards, democracy takes a step backwards!

This policy brief is aimed at elected and newly elected members of the European Parliament, the European Commission and its subcommittees, who are committed to defending and promoting the values of freedom, equality and democracy within the European Union and beyond.

It is now your role to act as a shield against attacks and the pushbacks, and to support feminist movements and organisations that are on the front line fighting for greater economic, social, environmental and sexual and reproductive justice.

The aim of our FIERCE project, Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe, is precisely to strengthen these organisations by providing sound knowledge and practical tools for revitalising alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision-makers, in the face of the strengthening of the anti-gender actors and rhetoric of the populist radical right and in a context of war, growing social inequality, climate crisis and political disaffection.

What is the FIERCE project?

By merging academic and action-based research conducted by national and transnational research laboratories (composed by researchers and feminist groups), in the 8 European countries partnering with the project (France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, Spain); FIERCE develops in-depth understanding and draws up a clear inventory of anti-gender movements and their impact on the institutional arena in five key areas: Labour market, Health and reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights, Migration and Gender-based violence. These data are crucial for effective action!

Beyond research and comparative cross-sectional analysis of these movements, FIERCE also studies demands, strategies and political influence of feminist movements. Based on the results of its research and on a strong alliance with feminist and civil society organizations, FIERCE develops and implements innovative pilot actions and projects that can reinvigorate democratic practices.

Building on the strength of our expertise and our bottom-up, problem-focused and impact-driven approach, we link academic knowledge, policy development and democratic strategies.

II. Anti-gender, anti-feminist: what are we talking about?

Key definitions

Gender: In the Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combatting violence against women and domestic violence, also known as “the Istanbul Convention”, adopted on 7 April 2011, the Council of Europe explains that the term ‘gender’ ‘refers to the socially constructed roles, behaviours, activities and attributes which a given society considers appropriate for women and men’. For the purposes of the Convention, gender refers to a system of social norms and roles attributed to individuals on the basis of the binary vision of biological sexes. This concept highlights the distinction between biological characteristics and cultural and social constructions of roles, behaviour, and identities. It is an analytical tool for understanding the relations of power and domination that exist between men and women. Gender is a social construct that perpetuates structural inequalities between the sexes. It is important to note, however, that identities go beyond the binary distinction of female and male, and also beyond the distinction between sex and gender (such as social class, sociological race, etc).¹

Gender equality is a fundamental principle that aims to ensure that individuals, regardless of their sex or gender identity, enjoy the same rights, responsibilities and opportunities in all spheres of life, free from violence and coercion. It goes beyond mere formal equality before the law; it seeks to eliminate the structural discrimination and gender stereotypes that perpetuate inequality. According to the

¹ The explanatory report, Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence, also known as “the Istanbul Convention” (2011) <https://rm.coe.int/1680a48903>

World Health Organisation (WHO), gender equality is essential for a sustainable, peaceful, prosperous and healthy world in which no one is left behind.²

From a feminist perspective, gender equality implies a profound transformation of the social, economic and political structures that perpetuate unequal power relations. It aims to deconstruct imposed gender roles and norms, to value the contributions of women and gender minorities, and to promote equal participation in decision-making at all levels. The Council of Europe emphasizes that gender equality means that the behaviour, aspirations, wishes and needs of women and men are equally valued and promoted.³

What are anti-gender and anti-feminist movements?

According to the mapping of key actors that we conducted in Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Turkey, we were able to see that anti-feminist and anti-gender movements are interconnected ideological and political

Several anti-gender and anti-feminist personalities present in the earlier Parliament have been (re)elected for a new mandate: Italian, French, Spanish, Dutch, Greek and Polish MEPs who have used their power to spread hateful messages and to oppose gender equality.

While one does not find “traditional” anti-feminist discourse among their statements, such as, for instance “a woman's job is in the kitchen”, some of these MEPs disagree on basic facts, such as the fact that in Europe there is – still – a problem of gender inequalities and gender-based violence.

In fact, this delicate and important theme is oftentimes treated by anti-gender actors by ignoring the structural problem of patriarchy and blaming external factors and actors, especially migrants.

Listen to what they said: ***Mr President, we are meeting today to consider a definition of gender-based violence, which would be a new area of crime. But why do we need a new definition and why this silence on the origin of these criminals? [...] Let's first think about these crimes, about these women far removed from any ideology.***

Virginie Joron, France, Rassemblement National, PFE
Definition of gender-based violence as a new area of crime listed in Article 83 TFEU, debate, 15/07/2021

forces opposing gender equality, LGBTQI+ rights, and sexual and reproductive health and rights.

Anti-feminist and anti-gender movements reject feminism's core principles, particularly its advocacy for equality, challenging feminist gains by asserting that traditional gender roles are “natural” and claiming that women's rights undermine men's societal status. These actors include religious groups, anti-abortion movements which proclaim themselves “pro-life” organizations, and men's rights movements, which historically targeted

² World Health Organization, *Gender equality makes everyone healthier: WHO*, March 2017,

<https://www.who.int/westernpacific/news/item/05-03-2017-gender-equality-makes-everyone-healthier-who>

³ The explanatory report, Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence, also known as “the Istanbul Convention” (2011) <https://rm.coe.int/1680a48903>

feminism directly. In recent years, many of these older groups have aligned with or adopted the rhetoric of anti-gender movements, amplifying their ideas and expanding their influence.

Since the 2010s, the anti-gender movements emerged in a coordinated opposition to what they term “gender ideology.” This term, an intentionally vague and alarmist construct, encompasses a wide range of social and legal advancements, including marriage equality, sex education, reproductive rights, and gender fluidity. Sometimes framed as a conspiracy theory, “gender ideology” is portrayed as a radical effort by feminists and LGBTQ+ activists to destabilize

society by rejecting biological essentialism and promoting social engineering. This framing allows disparate groups - such as religious institutions, nationalist parties,

conservative politicians, media figures, femonationalist⁴ organizations, masculinists and online communities — to unite under a shared opposition to perceived threats to traditional values.

These movements are highly organized and well-funded, forming extensive local and international networks. Notable examples include the spread of initiatives like France's "Manif pour tous" to Italy or the expansion of Polish think-tank Ordo Iuris into other countries. They also influence state policies in certain countries, such as

Poland, where anti-gender ideology is integrated into official politics. The actors involved range from grassroots “concerned citizens” groups to influential religious and political organizations, demonstrating the breadth and adaptability of their coalitions.

These movements represent a reactionary backlash against decades of progress in gender equality, seeking to entrench patriarchal and heteronormative norms. They not only threaten feminist achievements but also contribute to broader anti-democratic trends by undermining rights for women, LGBTQ+ communities, and other marginalized groups.

Following the overturn of *Roe v. Wade* in the United States as well as the recent developments in Polish and Hungarian law, the EP has approved a symbolic resolution that recognises the right to abortion as a fundamental European right. Of course, this decision has been highly contested by opponents to abortion rights, who disagree with the very definition of the right to abortion as a human right.

"Denying life to the unborn can never be considered a human right. It is an atrocity to try to legitimize it by seeking to create other so-called rights. What is contrary to the natural order cannot be considered a human right."

Margarita de la Pisa Carrion, Spain, Vox
PFE, member of FEMM Committee

The situation of fundamental rights in the European Union in 2022 and 2023, debate, 17/01/2024

⁴ Femonationalists or femonationalism is a concept coined by the researcher Sara R. Farris to refer to the use of feminist discourse by the far right, nationalists and neo-liberals for electoral, racist and xenophobic purposes. Sara R. Farris, “Femonationalism and the ‘Reserve’ Army of Labor Called Migrant Women”, *History of the Present*, vol. 2, n° 2, 2012, p. 184-199.

What is the « backlash »?

The concept of “backlash,” as articulated by Susan Faludi in 1991,⁵ describes the resistance and opposition that arise in response to significant progress in gender equality and feminist policies. This reactionary pushback often portrays advances in women's rights as excessive or harmful, leveraging claims that equality has already been achieved to justify halting further reforms. Backlash aims to roll back feminist achievements by fostering societal doubt about their necessity, framing them as threats to traditional values and stability.

This concept has since evolved and been paired with “backsliding,” which denotes a political reversal of democratization efforts, while “backlash” focuses on the regression of feminist policies.

LGBTQ+ rights, especially when regarding parenting rights of same sex couples, are attacked every day by anti-gender actors. They believe that the only possible kind of family is the so-called natural one, that is, the one in which a man and a woman get married and have kids. Of course, this ignores the factual reality that the natural family is now rarer than ever, and that the family is developing in forms and combinations that cannot be reduced to the natural family.

“Since the dawn of time and throughout the ages, having a family requires a man and a woman. [...] It is clear that the planned blow to the family as the fundamental nucleus of society hides other things behind it. We persist until the end. Children need a mother and a father. The normal family is irreplaceable. We say a firm NO to having children by same-sex couples.”

MEP Emmanouil (Fragkoulis) Fragkos, Greece, EL, ECR

In contemporary Europe, this backlash manifests through a pervasive narrative claiming that gender equality is fully realized. But in reality, we see significant cultural and legal assaults on the rights of women and LGBTQI+ individuals. Anti-gender movements have emerged, targeting feminists and LGBTQI+ activists as scapegoats for various social, political, and economic challenges. This has led to tangible setbacks in rights, particularly concerning bodily autonomy and reproductive freedoms, and in other areas.

Scholars like David Paternotte⁶ argue that this backlash should be viewed not merely as a response to feminist activism but as part of a broader conservative movement and agenda that threatens the rule of law, democratic norms and

values.

⁵ S. Faludi (1991) *Backlash. The Undeclared War Against American Women*, Crown Publishing Group.

⁶ D. Paternotte (2021) “Backlash: une mise en récit fallacieuse”, *La Revue Nouvelle*, 6, 11-15. <https://doi.org/10.3917/rn.216.0011>

Studying anti-gender mobilization is not limited to identifying the characteristics, actors, and strategies of this new movement that has developed over the last decade but touches on broader issues such as the decline of the public sphere and democratic norms (e.g., erosion of democratic argumentative debate, appropriation of public spheres by right-wing populist elites, crisis of trust in science, increasing individualization, etc.). The anti-gender movement contributes to contemporary authoritarian processes of de-democratization that target not

The rise of the right and the far-right in the European Parliament is also the consequence of a public debate more and more divided on the issue of migration. The urgency of an answer to what is perceived as an enormous problem allows for anti-gender actors even to be explicitly racist with migrants, especially Muslims. Islamophobia is used to change the discourse on gender equality.

This discourse is linked to the conspiracy theory of the ethnic substitution, which argues that a so-called invasion of migrants has the sole objective of substituting the European community, robbing it of its culture and identity.

“Mr President, dear colleagues, for decades now, so-called anti-racism has become a real religion, designed to make Europeans feel guilty and to make them accept what no other people accepts anywhere on the planet, that is to say, massive, anarchic immigration, the flows of which are increasing and against which it is now forbidden to speak out. [...] While certain ethnic, sexual or religious minorities are entitled to all the attention, while their demands, including those most incompatible with the general interest, are promoted and valued, there is a category which has no right to anything, apart from the right to be made to feel guilty, to self-flagellate: it is the European, white, Christian and heterosexual man.”

*Nicolas Bay, France, Reconquete
ECR*

*Racial justice, non-discrimination and anti-racism in the EU, debate,
10/11/2022*

only gender and equality but also the concept and practice of democracy. For this reason, as highlighted by Eszter Kováts, the anti-gender movement should not be understood primarily as a mobilization against equality but rather as a symptom of a larger systemic crisis of progressive politics and its complicity with neoliberal ideology.

The current backlash is steered by political leaders throughout the World:

Everywhere, on every continent, conservative, populist and anti-gender movements/governments are gaining ground and organising around a common agenda to erode hard-won human rights, threatening lives and decades of progress. In Argentina, populist President Javier Milei has abolished the Ministry of Gender Equality and the National Institute against Discrimination (INADI). He denies scientific evidence on climate change and wants to abolish the right to abortion. And in Hungary Viktor Orbán has tightened legislation in 2022 by forcing women to listen to the heartbeat of the fetus before an abortion.

Donald Trump's recent victory in the United States will have a devastating impact far beyond US borders, with consequences for gender equality on sexual and reproductive health rights,⁷ and on both the national and international stage. His first election in 2016 has already had a major impact on the rights of women and gender minorities, most notably with the reinstatement of the Global Gag Rule (which suspended US funding for access to abortion and for the fight against HIV internationally), but he also played a major role in the reversal of the Roe vs Wade ruling, which recognised the right to abortion at the federal level, in 2022.

These actions are just the beginning of what is to come in Trump's second term as he may implement 'Project 2025',⁸ an ultra-conservative plan to strengthen anti-gender laws and undermine sexual and reproductive rights. Written under the auspices of the highly influential ultra-conservative think-tank, the Heritage Foundation, the plan's aims include promoting an anti-choice and anti-LGBTQ+ agenda in international bodies such as the UN and attempting to redefine human rights by deviating from previously established international standards.

It also advocates US withdrawal from international organisations and traditional diplomatic alliances. This project would lead the United States, which is currently the leading donor of official development aid, to drastically cut its funding for gender equality and access to healthcare. With the rise of the far right in Europe, there is a risk that this project will serve as a model for far-right groups in the European Parliament and in the countries themselves.

The European Union was founded on the values of peace and equality, especially between men and women. In many respects, it is one of the most advanced regions in the world in terms of gender equality. At UN level, the European voice has helped to advance several international conventions in favour of gender equality and individual freedoms. Through its various prerogatives, the European Union has an impact on women's rights in all spheres of society, both within its Member States and internationally, through European diplomacy and its development aid policy.

In this context of far-right and anti-gender movement rising around the world, it is more than crucial that progressive voices join forces in a common front. In recent years, the European Union, like the rest of the world, has witnessed feminist and LGBTQIA+ mobilisations that have led to positive changes towards more egalitarian societies.

⁷ The Swedish Association for Sexuality Education (RFSU), Malayah Harper (2024) *GLOBAL IMPACTS OF PROJECT 2025 - How the blueprint for the next Republican administration may impact US foreign and development policy on SRHR and gender equality*

<https://www.rfsu.se/globalassets/pdf/project-2025/global-impacts-of-project-2025.pdf>

The EU Legal Framework on Gender Equality

At European level, several **fundamental texts** enshrine the **principle of gender equality**.

Article 23 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union states that 'equality between men and women must be ensured in all areas, including employment, work and pay'. Similarly, **Article 157 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)** guarantees equal pay for men and women workers for equal work or work of equal value.

In addition, **Article 14 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR)** prohibits any discrimination, including on the grounds of sex, in the enjoyment of the rights guaranteed by the Convention, thus consolidating the European commitment to equal treatment.

These legal texts provide a **legal framework** for or the promotion and protection of gender equality within the Member States of the European Union.

The EU has been particularly active on these issues in recent years, adopting and implementing a number of measures and instruments to promote gender equality, in both its internal and external policies.

A key example is the entry into force, for the **European Union, of the Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence or Istanbul Convention** on 1 October 2023. The Istanbul Convention is a legally binding treaty which imposes on its parties minimum standards and actions to be taken in the prevention, protection and prosecution of such violence.

The Union has also adopted the **Directive 2006/54/EC** aiming to strengthen equal treatment between men and women in the field of employment and occupation. It establishes clear obligations to prevent discrimination and promote real equality in access to employment, working conditions and career opportunities.

In 2020, the Commission adopted a new **EU Action Plan on Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment in External Action 2021-2025 (GAP III)**, which renews the EU's external action in favour of gender equality through an intersectional, gender-transformative and human rights-based approach. In particular, GAP III commits the EU to strengthening collaboration with civil society organisations, increasing funding for women's rights organisations and women's movements, and ensuring that 85% of all its new external relations actions contribute to gender equality and women's empowerment by 2025.

Finally, noting the increase in LGBTQIA+phobic discrimination and acts and the disparity in the protection of LGBTQIA+ people between Member States, in November 2020 the Commission launched the first **EU Strategy for Equality of LGBTQIA+ People 2020-2025**, hailed by part of LGBTQIA+ civil society as a strong signal and a turning point. Among other things, this strategy mentions making EU funding to Member States conditional on compliance with European law, particularly in terms of equality and non-discrimination.

III. What are the consequences and impact?

Actors of the backlash have turned feminists and LGBTQI+ activists into their scapegoat, holding them responsible for all current social, political and economic issues. This has resulted in actual setbacks in rights and a global endangerment of previous achievements, especially when it comes to bodily autonomy and sexual and reproductive health and rights (SRHR).

Back in 2017 already, the Council of Europe warned that women's sexual and reproductive rights were under threat, as several of its members sought to restrict legislation on access to abortion and contraception.

2 women are killed every day by a partner or family member
Council of the European Union, 2023⁹

Since then, many European countries have reported attempts to overturn existing laws on sexual and reproductive health and rights, including abortion rights, comprehensive sexuality education, assisted reproductive technologies and equal rights for members of the LGBTQIA+ community.

In 2020, **Poland drastically restricted the right to abortion** (already very restrictive). Poland has one of Europe's most restrictive abortion laws. Together with Malta, it is one of only two European Union Member States that has not legalized abortion on request or broad social grounds. In Poland, abortion was only permitted in situations of risk to the life or health of a pregnant woman, or if a pregnancy resulted from rape. On 22 October 2020, Poland's Constitutional Tribunal ruled that even abortion on grounds of "severe and irreversible fetal defect or incurable illness that threatens the fetus' life" was unconstitutional.

In February 2024, **Italy's Prime Minister Giorgia Meloni introduced a law making the use of a surrogate mother abroad a "universal crime"** (although surrogacy was already banned), and in April 2024, she pushed through a law allowing anti-abortion activists access to public consultation clinics through which women must pass to access abortion.

⁹ Council of Europe (2024) Infographics *Ending violence against women*

<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/fr/infographics/figures-gender-based-violence/>

Violence against women and sexual and gender minorities has increased steadily over the past five years,¹⁰ according to the European Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA).

In Hungary, the conservative and nationalist Prime Minister Viktor Orbán passed a **law in June 2021 to ban “propaganda” of homosexuality or gender reassignment among minors.** On July 1, 2021, **Turkey withdrew from the Istanbul Convention.** In France, the number of victims of domestic violence recorded in 2022 rose by 15% compared to 2021.

The FIERCE project points out that many other areas are under threat, for example in the workplace. **According to the 2023 Pay Transparency Directive, the gender pay gap averaged around 13% in the EU in 2020,**¹¹ meaning that women will earn on average 13% less per hour than men. The pay gap has a long-term impact on women's quality of life, their risk of falling into poverty, and the persistent retirement pension gap of around 30% in the EU (2018 data).

Even the most progressive countries with proclaimed feminist diplomacy are backtracking, with Sweden dropping out and other governments, such as the Netherlands, withdrawing.

The gender pay gap averaged around 13% in the EU in 2020

These attacks have a direct impact on activists and organizations.

Feminist actors, such as female politicians and researchers, have suffered personal attacks that hinder their participation in democratic processes. Digital tools have been the site of much violence: cyber-harassment, cybersexism, masculinist attacks, etc., which seek to discredit the voices of women and gender minorities.

This conclusion is shared by the latest Gender Equality Index (2023), which states that *“persistent gender gaps demonstrate the need for policy objectives that take a broader view of gender equality in different spheres of life, while designing policy actions to tackle gender inequalities in a specific area.”*

In the face of this “backlash”, it is important to remain mobilized, strengthen feminist and progressive movements and continue to demand profound changes in our societies.

¹⁰ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (2024) EU LGBTIQ survey III, *LGBTIQ at a crossroads: progress and challenges*, https://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra_uploads/fra-2024-lgbtiq-equality_en.pdf

¹¹ Council of Europe (2023) Infographics on pay transparency *Why pay transparency can help reduce the EU's gender pay gap*, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/infographics/pay-transparency/>

IV. What can you do for the upcoming mandate? - Our recommendations

The EU has championed women's rights and SRHR and this must continue. As an MEP, you can take many actions across a wide range of policy areas within EU competences, to advance gender equality in the next five years.

FIERCE asks you to:

1. Support European Feminist Networks that promote human rights

Feminist organisations and movements have always been and still are at the heart of the struggle for gender equality, but also at the heart of the struggle for greater justice and rights. This has been the case in Iran, and also in Poland, where protests against restrictions on women's rights have led to more massive mobilisations to defend the respect for democracy and the rule of law. Most feminist organizations do not have sufficient resources to carry out their actions and are operating on a voluntary basis. They need you to:

- amplify feminist voices in the EU institutions by establishing a collaborative process that facilitates networking and alliance-building opportunities among existing national and transnational feminist movements and NGOs and building a STRONG front that the European Parliament systematically supports and empowers.
- Guarantee constant, sustainable and long-term core funding (not exclusively project-based) for feminist activists and rights advocacy organisations, movements, and networks to secure their actions and move beyond the uncertainty of volunteering. While it is difficult to have a clear and complete picture of the funding that actually goes to feminist organisations, only 0.5%

Only 0.5% of European Union official development assistance funding focused on equality went to women's rights organisations or gender equality institutions (OECD, 2023)¹²

¹² Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2023) *Aid in Support of Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment - DONOR CHARTS*

<https://web-archiver.oecd.org/2023-03-07/634734-Aid-to-gender-equality-donor-charts.pdf>

of European Union official development assistance funding focused on equality (cad 1 and 2) went to women's rights organisations or gender equality institutions (OECD, 2023). Comparatively, from 2009 to 2018, nearly 700 million dollars went to anti-gender campaigns in Europe and 437 million dollars from the European Union were spent on anti-gender/anti-choice movements between 2009 and 2018 (EPF, 2021).¹³

- Realising a detailed monitoring and assessment of the share of EU funding that goes to women's and gender minority rights would also be a good way of assessing EU and national institutions.

2. Better identifying and combating Anti-gender movements

To gain a better understanding of the political support available to anti-gender movements and to effectively measure the funding they receive from the EU, in order to put an end to them, it is essential to:

- Track and monitor their funding from the EU institutions. The European Union shall efficiently prevail its finances to support effectively the Goals and Values it intends to defend. These recommendations are in line with those formulated by Ljijana Loncar advisor to the Serbian Deputy Prime Minister and President of the Coordination Body for Gender Equality, in her communication "Gender Equality Backlash" in May 2019.

437 million dollars from the European Union were spent on anti-gender/anti-choice movements between 2009 and 2018 (EPF, 2021).

- Prevent the spread of anti-gender discourses and narratives
- Systematically monitor and denounce hate speech based on anti-gender and antifeminist rhetoric, which includes violent discourse against women, misogynistic attacks on female politicians, gender-based threats against female journalists, women human rights defenders, discrimination attacks on LGBTQI+, hatred against marginalized groups, etc. within the European bodies but also in policies.

¹³ European Parliamentary Forum, Neil Datta (2021) *Tip of the Iceberg: Religious Extremist Funders against Human Rights for Sexuality & Reproductive Health in Europe*, <https://www.epfweb.org/sites/default/files/2021-08/Tip%20of%20the%20Iceberg%20August%202021%20Final.pdf>

3. Confront online democracy threats such as disinformation and hate speech

Anti-gender and antifeminist discourse is responsible for online and offline violence of many people when threats escalate to a personal level. Political discourse should create a narrative that directly connects the feminist agenda and democracy.

- Document and expose gender biases in technology, AI and social media algorithms. Promote using tools and systems that foster algorithmic justice.
- Regulate digital platforms' criteria for identifying non-democratic threats and guarantee that the algorithm-building process respects European values, using fair and transparent algorithm management tools.
- Advocate intersectional criteria in the analysis of information presented by the media so its coverage shifts towards diversity, considering gender, ethnicity, religion, ideology, and other identity markers.

4. Support the implementation of legislation supporting women and gender rights

- Develop a Europe that pursues a feminist foreign policy that defends SRHR in multilateral bodies and supports feminist organisations in the face of the rise of anti-choice movements and the extreme right.
- Defend a Europe that pays specific attention to people at the intersection of several forms of discrimination (LGBTQIA+ people, migrants, sex workers, etc.). Women, girls and LGBTQIA+ people and those who find themselves at the intersection of several discriminations are the populations most affected by discrimination by war, climate and migration crises, social inequalities, etc., and must be given special attention in public policies.
- Reproductive justice goes beyond fundamental reproductive rights, encompassing aspects such as maintaining personal bodily autonomy, freedom of choice in childbearing (including LGBTQI+ people) and the right to abortion, access to childcare, and issues related to adoption. These vital rights must be accessible to racialised and minoritised women, women with disabilities, those affected by poverty, and any other inequalities. The reason behind this inequality is simple – marginal groups don't have full access to their rights. A particular emphasis should be put on female genital mutilation (FGM) and combating forced sterilisation, one of the most serious human rights violations that have been documented regarding Romani women and

LGBTQI+ people. JUSTICE means JUSTICE FOR EVERYBODY as a universal model, and no specific population group should be excluded.

- Constitutionalise reproductive rights at the EU level and modify the Charter of Fundamental Rights and the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU), in line with European Parliament proposals. Ensure that the EU is up-to-date with the latest reproductive issues in the Member States and that legislation is modified accordingly.

You will find all our recommendations on the FIERCE campaign website :

<https://fierce-project.eu>

<https://euroalter.com/journal/five-fierce-claims-for-a-feminist-europe/>

[Factsheet - Gender equality under attack The normalisation of anti-gender movements in Europe]

Key results of the FIERCE project (2010-2023)

Introduction

In recent years, Europe has witnessed a major transnational reinforcement and mainstreaming of the anti-feminist and anti-gender mobilisations, which are consolidating as influential political forces capable of impacting laws, policies and dominant narratives.

The **FIERCE** Research project - *Feminist Movements Revitalising Democracy in Europe* - analysed anti-feminist and anti-gender movements **between 2010 and 2023 in eight European countries** (Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain and Turkey) with the aim of mapping actors, and understanding how they organise, what narratives they mobilise, and how they contribute to de-democratisation of Europe and thereby threaten our democracies.

Methodology

The research is based on **methodological triangulation** combining qualitative and quantitative approaches, including literature reviews, critical frame analysis, social network analysis and mapping media and anti-gender mobilisations. A total of 41 interviews were conducted with anti-feminist and anti-gender actors, covering the eight countries. The cross-cutting analysis focused on six central themes: Labor market, gender-based violence, LGBTQI+ rights, education, migration, and health and reproductive rights.

A heterogeneous coalition with converging objectives

The research highlights a series of actors opposed to gender equality, brought together in a strategically coordinated coalition. These alliances include conservative or right-wing political parties, religious organisations and churches, conservative family-oriented or anti-abortion civil society organisations (CSOs), transnational networks, masculinist, anti-gender “feminists” (TERFs, alter-feminists) and femonationalist groups.

Despite their different statuses, ideologies, modes of action and degrees of influence, these actors share a **common opposition to what they refer to as “gender ideology”** - a deliberately vague concept mobilised against all equality politics and attacking specifically the rights of women, LGBTQIA+ and trans people.

In most cases, **right-wing political parties were identified as the main advocates of anti-feminist and anti-gender positions**, closely followed by CSOs and advocacy groups.

An ideological offensive structured around six strategic areas

Our data shows **six** priority **areas**, identified as strategic by anti-gender groups in all the countries in the study. These are not marginal opinions, but **deliberate areas of political intervention**, supported by campaigns, alliances and legislative proposals:

- **Defense of the “traditional family”**

In all countries, respondents stressed the importance of preserving the 'traditional family', defined as a heterosexual nuclear unit with strictly defined roles for men and women. In Poland, Greece and Italy, for example, anti-gender actors largely based their discourse on religious values, with Catholicism and Orthodoxy serving as ideological reference points. Conversely, in Denmark and France anti-gender actors rely more on secular conservative ideologies, focusing more on cultural preservation rather than on the religious framework.

- **Opposition to gender equality policies**

Gender equality is presented as a hegemonic ideology promoted by feminists, who are accused of blurring gendered reference points or threatening masculinity. In France, this discourse is linked to criticism of "neo-feminism", which is accused of creating a social imbalance to the detriment of men. In Denmark, the respondents saw prejudice against men in gender equality policies, describing feminism as exclusionary; while in Italy and Greece, TERFS and alter-feminists critical of gender oppose the very concept of gender, which they see as calling into question biological realities.

- **Rejection of the rights of LGBTQIA+ people**

Opposition to LGBTQIA+ rights is widespread within these mobilisations, with the diversity of gender identities and sexual orientations being denied and equated with deviance or a threat to existing social and cultural norms. The most controversial issues are those relating to marriage, adoption, gender identity, access to the labour market, and surrogacy. In Turkey, LGBTQIA+ visibility is presented as foreign propaganda threatening national values, and the country goes as far as to criminalise activism by banning LGBTQIA+ associations' activities. In recent years, throughout Europe, this opposition has especially been fuelled by attacks on the rights of trans people.

- **Questioning sexual and reproductive health and rights (SRHR)**

The intensity of attacks on SRHRs varies enormously from country to country, but the right to abortion is a recurring and central target. While in Poland this opposition is deeply rooted in religious teachings, in other countries anti-gender activists link abortion directly to demographic decline and advocate pro-natalist policies.

- **Control of education and school content**

Education has also become a battleground for the anti-gender movement in several countries. Schools are seen as places of ideological indoctrination, where content relating to gender or sexuality is accused of threatening children's innocence. In Slovenia, parental guides have been produced to denounce LGBTQIA+ "infiltration" of schools. In Turkey, gender equality policies in the education sector have been cancelled. In Greece, where matters of education and religion are governed by the same ministry, the state still refuses to introduce comprehensive sexuality education in schools.

- **Xenophobic discourse and racism**

Migration is instrumentalised as a threat to national identity, with cultural assimilation and perceived moral decline attributed to foreign influences. In Greece, anti-immigration rhetoric revolves around the fear of Islamisation and loss of national identity. In France, immigration is associated with sexual violence in conservative narratives, producing a tension between gender equality and cultural security.

In each national context, these six themes are formulated and prioritised differently, according to local historical, political and religious dynamics.

While these issues manifest themselves at a structural level, anti-gender actors attribute their emergence to broader superstructural factors, including liberalism, globalisation, individualism, secularisation and what they perceive to be a distorted interpretation of gender equality. These

underlying factors are presented as the root causes of their specific actions in the six areas identified.

A coordinated strategy of institutional and media influence

FIERCE identifies a **coherent set of tactics** that enable anti-gender actors to extend their influence within political institutions, media spaces and public opinion.

- **Alliance with conservative parties and legislative lobbying**

Anti-gender coalitions rely on **strategic alliances with right-wing populist or religious parties**, aiming either to restrict existing laws or propose new ones. In Poland, the **Ordo Iuris** organisation has directly contributed to the drafting of legislation challenging women's rights, while in Slovenia anti-gender actors have successfully used referenda to oppose same-sex partnerships. In Turkey, they attempted to sway public opinion to support the presidential decree withdrawing the country from the Istanbul Convention. In Greece, there has been a regress in child custody legislation, achieved through intense lobbying by Men's Rights Activists.

- **Strategic use of media and language**

One of the main strategies is to involve the public and the media in shaping the narrative. Using social media, messaging apps and so-called "alternative" platforms, particularly the manosphere and "alter-feminists" are seeking to bypass the "mainstream media", in order to amplify their visibility and often organise events to stir up controversy and secure media coverage. In France and Slovenia, stories about schools "contaminated" by gender are circulating massively on social networks.

Our findings show that anti-gender movements deliberately adapt and formulate their narratives so that they have a specific contextual resonance. These groups develop messages that align with local cultural and political concerns, often positioning themselves as protectors of tradition, national identity, biological norms or even 'true' gender equality.

- **Tactical imitation of the feminist and LGBTQIA+ movements**

Another major finding is that contemporary anti-gender movements frequently adopt and imitate the tactics used by feminist and LGBTQIA+ activists, a phenomenon termed "mirror strategies". Some pro-family groups in Italy present themselves as "defenders of women's rights" against surrogacy or abortion. In Slovenia, collectives are mobilising human rights slogans to challenge gender equality. In Greece, Men's Rights Groups often reverse feminist discourse, by claiming that it's actually men that are suffering from gender-based violence and oppression. By borrowing feminist and LGBTQIA+ symbols and language, they blur the lines between their ideologies and progressive movements, complicating public perception and undermining the real feminist and LGBTQIA+ objectives.

- **Production of alternative knowledge and pseudo-scientific legitimization**

Anti-gender movements are also investing in the educational **field** to produce "alternative" facts and "alternative" knowledge presented as expertise, using legal or quasi-scientific language to **cloak reactionary claims in neutrality**. In France, Greece, and Turkey, reports purporting to be "independent studies" denounce the negative impact of equality policies or construct evidence for gender-based violence predominantly against men. Pseudo-scientific claims like "Parental Alienation Syndrome" are used to maintain authority over abused children and former partners. Misguided approaches to biology are often used by TERFs to alienate and suppress trans individuals.

- **Transnational cooperation and pooling of tactics**

Structured platforms such as **Vision Network (formerly Agenda Europe)** enable **the circulation of discourse, financial resources and tools** from one country to another. Campaigns on "gender ideology" are taken up and adapted from Rome to Warsaw, from Ljubljana to Madrid.

Essentialist, emotional and performative rhetoric

Anti-gender activists mobilise a **range of powerful emotions** - fear, anger, moral panic - used to construct an **image of a society under threat** from feminism, gender equality and the rights of LGBTQIA+ people. They establish a permanent crisis narrative, justifying authoritarian interventions in the name of common sense, nature or morality. The research found that parliamentary debates tend to be more emotionally charged, particularly in discussions about abortion, while social movement documents often display a wider range of deceptively empathetic or protective emotions, particularly in a religious context, where moral duty and responsibility are invoked. Several dominant frameworks run through all the countries studied:

- **Protection of the child** - is a recurring term, a moral imperative used in every country to justify the control of knowledge, the rejection of diversity and the surveillance of non-normative families. Sex education is denounced as an intrusion into the parental sphere.
 - **Natural law** - in which gender roles are described as **fixed, immutable and ordered by God or biology**, justifying social hierarchisation and exclusion. In Poland and Turkey, this law is explicitly religious. In Italy, Slovenia and Denmark, it takes a “rationalist” form, based on biological arguments.
 - **Reversing stigma and strategic victimization** - anti-gender actors often present themselves as oppressed minorities of opinion, muzzled by the feminist, LGBTQIA+ or cosmopolitan “lobby”. They present their perspectives as minority voices in need of protection in a diverse society, while defending exclusionary beliefs. In France, the rhetoric of “cancel culture” is used to criticise feminist and anti-racist movements. In Denmark, “political correctness” is denounced as an ideological dogma to be deconstructed.
 - **The fusion of religious and nationalist registers** - Moral rhetoric draws on religious traditions while at the same time taking on a nationalist register. The role of religion varies considerably from country to country. In Poland, Greece, Spain, and Turkey, religion is deeply rooted in the family, morality and nationalism, reinforcing the argument that progressive change undermines national and cultural cohesion. In contrast, the French and Danish discourses are entirely secular and focus on cultural and political critiques rather than religious imperatives.
- Usurpation of the language of human rights** - Anti-gender actors **hijack the key concepts of liberal democracy** - freedom, pluralism, human rights - to legitimise exclusionary positions under the guise of rationality and neutrality. It is a process of **de-democratisation**, the extent of which our research contributes to demonstrate.

A structured ideological project with an authoritarian vision of democracy

Anti-gender mobilisations are not simply one-off reactions: they are part of a coherent ideological project that naturalizes social hierarchies, redefines democracy in an authoritarian key and uses pseudo-democratic language to defend traditional norms.

Supported by national and transnational networks, this movement aims to restructure the democratic space in a reactionary direction. This is not a simple disagreement of opinions, but a confrontation between two visions of society: one egalitarian, plural and democratic; the other hierarchical, authoritarian and exclusive. The institutions and defenders of equality must take measure of this: it requires increased vigilance, rigorous documentation and lasting transnational solidarity.

Our recommendations:

Political recommendations were elaborated by feminist collectives from throughout Europe in a collaborative research-action framework happening within the transnational feminist labs and network:

Monitoring and countering anti-gender movements

- Identify and map European funding that directly or indirectly benefits anti-gender actors. Put an end to this funding by ensuring that it complies with EU values.
- Publicly sanction hate speech and attacks on the rights of women, LGBTQIA+ people and human rights defenders.
- Strengthen digital safety: reporting procedures, rapid removal of sexist, homophobia, transphobic etc. content, media codes of conduct.

Strengthening feminist movements in Europe

- Ensure sustainable and structural core funding for feminist organisations, beyond one-off projects.
- Actively support transnational feminist networks: networking, alliances, political visibility in European institutions.
- Accurately monitor financial flows: introduce transparent monitoring of the actual funding allocated to women's and gender minorities' rights.

Protecting democracy in the face of digital attacks

- Regulate digital platforms to counter sexist and anti-feminist misinformation.
- Promote algorithmic justice: auditing gender bias in technologies and guaranteeing the transparency of moderation criteria.

[Factsheet - Feminist movements in Europe: a democratic force against the backlash]

Main results of the FIERCE project (2010-2023)

Introduction

Between 2010 and 2023, Europe saw **an intensification of feminist mobilisations** while at the same time social inequalities continued to rise. The feminist movements, far from being homogenous, share a common desire to **reaffirm equality as a democratic foundation**, by articulating intersectional demands, innovative practices and a systemic critique of power structures.

The **FIERCE** (Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe) project has carried out in-depth research in eight European countries (Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain and Turkey) to understand how feminist movements are organised, which strategies they deploy and how they influence democracy.

Methodology

As part of this research, we used an **interdisciplinary and comparative approach**, combining interviews, campaign analysis and discourse mapping. This methodology enabled us to analyse the **transnational dynamics** as well as the **local specificities** of feminist mobilisations. A total of 240 interviews were conducted (163 with feminist activists and 69 with politicians who support feminist initiatives).

Feminist mobilisation in Europe: interconnected struggles against structural domination

Across the eight countries, feminist movements are converging on the structural nature of gender-based oppression. From gender-based violence (GBV) to reproductive justice, from LGBTQIA+ rights to economic inequality, these movements are defending rights, autonomy and dignity - not as isolated but as intertwined issues, in a broader struggle against patriarchy, neoliberalism and authoritarian drift. The main issues dealt with are:

- **Combating gender-based violence**

Sexual and domestic violence has remained at the heart of feminist mobilisations in recent years. In Spain, Italy, Slovenia, France, Turkey, and Poland, activists explicitly present gender-based violence as a symptom of patriarchal structures, deeply rooted in law, culture and institutions. Feminist movements have contributed to major legal reforms (such as the ratification of the Istanbul Convention or the adoption of consent-based laws to redefine rape and sexual violence) but the gaps between symbolic recognition and concrete protection persist.

- **Promoting reproductive justice and bodily autonomy**

Sexual and reproductive health and rights (SRHR) are a recurring concern, in particular the right to abortion. Even when abortion is legal, there are many **informal obstacles**, including **conscientious**

objection, limited access, medical violence and so on. In Poland, Slovenia, Turkey, Italy and Spain, feminist organisations have mobilised to fight attempts to restrict the right to abortion.

- **Defending the rights of LGBTQIA+ people**

In almost all the cases studied, alliances between feminist and LGBTQIA+ collectives (when they are not linked within the same organisation) are aimed at equality and access to new rights by law (legal recognition of same sex couples and queer parenthood, rights to have a family). Some victories have been achieved. In Slovenia, for example, same-sex marriage was legalised in 2022, and in France access for all women to medically assisted procreation was attained in 2021. Throughout the case studies, alliances have also often focused on the legalisation and recognition of gender identity.

- **Combating economic inequality**

Contemporary feminist movements are paying renewed attention to the **material conditions of existence**, arguing for **equal pay, recognition of care work**, the right to housing and economic security. In Turkey, activists target policies that reproduce poverty, while in Spain, precarious work conditions of migrant domestic workers have been a main focus. **Care work** was also at the centre of feminist strikes in France, Italy and Spain.

- **The intersectional approach, a new central framework and an area of conflict**

Intersectionality is a fundamental framework for analysis, particularly in Spain, France, Turkey, Greece, Italy and Slovenia. Conceptualised by Kimberlé Crenshaw, this paradigm makes it possible to think about overlapping oppressions –sexism, racism, ableism, transphobia and classism-. In Greece, activists are documenting the specific violence suffered by refugee and migrant women. But in some countries, this concept is the subject of strong antagonism. In France, the intersectional perspective has led to tensions between a new generation of activists and those loyal to traditional universalist approaches. In Denmark, the approach has earlier been marginal in mainstream feminist discourse but is increasingly becoming more prominent through cross-cutting alliances in civil society and innovative campaigns.

Organisational forms and adaptation dynamics

- **Structural diversity: between autonomy and institutionalisation**

Feminist movements in Europe are characterised by great structural and organisational diversity. Movements fluctuate between **professionalisation (NGOs)** and the **maintenance of horizontal, autonomous and intersectional forms**. In Italy, Spain and Greece, feminist organisations generally maintain **grassroots, non-hierarchical structures** in order to preserve their autonomy from official political institutions. In other contexts, such as Denmark or France, feminist action has a more institutional dimension, with NGOs and CSOs working within established political frameworks, often engaging in advocacy, service provision, or policy monitoring. Many organisations adopt a hybrid posture, combining autonomous activist practices and institutional dialogue.

- **Strategic adaptability to changing environments**

Feminist movements in Europe have demonstrated a strong capacity to adapt, in response to uneven and changing political contexts. In countries where SRHR are legally recognised - such as France and Slovenia - they fight for their effective application. Conversely, in more repressive contexts - such as Poland or Turkey - they adopt more discreet strategies: informal networks, mutual aid, or protective practices.

This adaptability is not just defensive. It is based on a subtle link between urgency and prefiguration: responding rapidly to attacks (on abortion rights, LGBTQ+ rights, etc.) while building sustainable forms of organisation, such as training facilities, solidarity networks and legal resources.

Feminists also know how to mobilise on a transnational scale. Slogans such as Ni Una Menos and #MeToo are reappropriated locally (in Italy, Spain, Denmark and Slovenia), not as models, but as mobilisation resources adapted to national contexts. This circulation of ideas and practices enables feminist activists to think locally and globally, to build alliances across borders and to respond collectively to anti-gender offensives. Strong transnational solidarity is also demonstrated by the 2024 campaign *My Voice, My Choice*, initiated by a Slovenian feminist collective, which gathered over 1 million signatures in support of safeguarding abortion rights across Europe.

Feminist adaptability is anything but a retreat: it is a situated, inventive and collective political practice that enables these movements to endure, to act and to open futures.

Practices and repertoires of action: between resistance and political invention

Feminist movements deploy a broad, rich and evolving repertoire of action, combining resistance to existing systems of domination with the invention of alternative political and social practices. They do not simply resist but propose transformative **forms of narrative and repertoire of action. Street demonstrations remain a mainstay** - whether against sexist violence in France or the restriction of SRHR in Poland. But they are only one mode of action. Movements are also investing in autonomous **training**: workshops, feminist schools, intersectional pedagogies. These spaces transmit knowledge, histories and tools of resistance outside institutional frameworks.

Other tools, although already in use, are central to feminist action, according to FIERCE research.

Artistic expression - performances, choreographies, theatrical actions - plays a central role in the construction of a feminist presence in the public space. The innovative use of performance was highlighted in many of the cases studied in Italy, Greece and Slovenia. These actions are not merely symbolic; they channel emotions, memory and collective identity into the public space, creating new forms of visibility and commitment.

Feminist activists are deploying a combined strategic use of digital and traditional media to raise awareness and extend the reach of action. Feminist activists are using social networks not only to raise awareness, but also to create alternative spaces for deliberation, solidarity and collective action across borders (in France, Slovenia, Turkey, Greece and Spain). In several cases, digital campaigns serve as a springboard for offline organising, enabling feminists to bypass the filters of traditional media and reach marginalised groups. At the same time, activists report an increase in online attacks, disinformation and surveillance, prompting them to develop new forms of digital security, content moderation strategies and collective defence mechanisms.

A striking dynamic runs through all the fields studied: the building of inter-struggle alliances. The feminist organisations studied show **real coherence and ideological consistency** in their fight for equality, social justice and democracy, and are building **cross-cutting alliances** with the anti-racist, trade-union, homosexual and migrant movements. In France, alliances have been forged between feminist, anti-racist, gay and trade union organisations, notably around opposition to austerity or discriminatory policies. In Poland, the defence of reproductive rights was closely linked to broader campaigns in favour of the rule of law and democratic freedoms. These coalitions, though sometimes fragile, reflect a shared political vision: feminist struggles are at the heart of contemporary democratic resistance. They do not add to other struggles - they link them.

Feminist movements also mobilise **affect, emotion and lived experience as central resources for political action**. In the face of neutralising conservative rhetoric or technocratic narratives, feminists are asserting that emotion is political - that it enables injustice to be named, institutional silences to be denounced and more humane and deep-rooted forms of resistance to be nurtured. Anger, frustration and fear are used by feminist actors to signal the urgency of threats - particularly in response to anti-gender narratives or institutional inaction. At the same time, emotions such as **caring, empathy and solidarity** are deployed to foster inclusive communities, support traumatised people and build lasting trust between organisations. In Greece, public mourning performances and tributes to the victims of femicide and the murder of LGBTQIA+ persons are becoming acts of resistance. Elsewhere, talking circles, support rituals and psychological care spaces are being created to sustain mobilisation over the long term. These "affective infrastructures" are fundamental to building resilient, intergenerational communities rooted in reciprocity.

Tensions with the institutions: between symbolic openness and political lock-in

Despite the growing visibility of feminist demands in the public arena, the activists interviewed expressed a widely shared frustration at the difficulty of translating this recognition into lasting structural change. While the contexts vary, a common observation emerges as institutions oscillate between rhetorical openness and political lock-in.

- **Variable openness of political systems: between recognition and inaction**

In most countries, feminist concerns such as gender-based violence, SRHR, or gender equality are officially recognised in political discourse. In countries with consolidated democratic mechanisms, feminist actors have participated in legislative processes, political consultations and public scrutiny. These commitments have contributed to concrete results, such as comprehensive laws on violence against women or greater recognition of LGBTQIA+ rights. However, the gap between rhetoric and action remains wide: the mechanism to implement the laws adopted are often underfunded, poorly implemented or fragile in the face of political upheaval. In France and Denmark, activists note that government actors often invoke "women's rights" as general principles, while avoiding to engage in structural criticism or intersectional perspectives. This form of symbolic politics generates fatigue and mistrust.

In more restricted civic spaces such as Turkey or Poland, the space for action is drastically reduced: **surveillance, criminalisation and public defamation** become tools of dissuasion. Access to institutions is limited, and feminist organisations are often forced into a defensive posture, limiting their ability to pursue proactive strategies and rights expansion. Still, activists in Turkey capitalize on the fragmented nature of governance between the central and the local levels and collaborate with municipalities run by opposition parties.

In many countries, interviewees point to the instrumentalisation of feminist discourse by anti-gender and far-right movements for strategic purposes - selectively invoking gender equality to signal progressivism while promoting anti-feminist positions or aiming to exclude other marginalised groups (e.g., racialised or transgender communities).

- **In the face of authoritarian regression, feminism as an essential democratic force**

Feminist struggles go well beyond the sectoral or identity-based framework. In the eight countries studied, they have emerged as **a bulwark against de-democratisation**, linking the fight against violence, economic injustice, racism, homophobia and authoritarian excesses.

Through their actions, feminist movements are not content simply to resist. They **propose a different vision of politics**, based on solidarity, recognition of interdependence and radical democracy. They reach out to the margins, forge alliances and experiment with forms of collective action that are rooted in lived experience and open to the political imagination.

In a Europe faced with the rise of anti-gender rhetoric and the weakening of democratic institutions, **feminists play a central role**: as watchdogs, innovators and catalysts for democratic renewal. Their full recognition is **a necessary condition** for any policy of progress and justice.

Our recommendations:

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Monitoring and countering anti-gender movements

- Identify and map European funding that directly or indirectly benefits anti-gender actors.
- Put an end to this funding by ensuring that it complies with EU values.
- Publicly sanction hate speech and attacks on the rights of women, LGBTQIA+ people and human rights defenders.
- Strengthen digital safety: reporting procedures, rapid removal of sexist content, media codes of conduct.

Strengthening feminist movements in Europe

- Ensure sustainable and structural core funding for feminist organisations, beyond one-off projects.
- Actively support transnational feminist networks: networking, alliances, political visibility in European institutions.
- Accurately monitor financial flows: introduce transparent monitoring of the actual funding allocated to women's and gender minorities' rights.

Protecting democracy in the face of digital attacks

- Regulate digital platforms to counter sexist and anti-feminist misinformation.
- Promote algorithmic justice: auditing gender bias in technologies and guaranteeing the transparency of moderation criteria.

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